

USING INNOVATIVE MARKETING STRATEGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MARKET OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES

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Abstract: The social dimension of ICT can be recapped with the emergence of the new modes of human behavior and communication. These widespread developments in the ICT field have significantly upgraded the way people interact and communicate with each other.

Key words: development, marketing, information, human, service, technologies, economy.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ МАРКЕТИНГОВЫХ СТРАТЕГИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ РЫНКА ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-КОММУНИКАЦИОННЫХ УСЛУГ

Аннотация: Социальное измерение ИКТ можно охарактеризовать с появлением новых способов человеческого поведения и общения. Эти широко распространенные разработки в области ИКТ значительно улучшили способы взаимодействия и общения людей друг с другом.

Ключевые слова: развитие, маркетинг, информация, человек, сервис, технологии, экономика.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of information and communication technologies (ICT) in a global economy that have resulted in the development of such innovations like computers, mobile phones and web technologies have fundamentally upgraded the services sector. As a result, the value production in the context of the gross national product (GNP) has in relative terms substantially moved from the agricultural sector and from the goods production sector to the services sector. Consequently, the digital transformation of organizational and economic principles of management became as one of the key factors of the global economic growth. The share of digital economy in the GDP of developed countries in 2010 was 1.2 percent, while this number have reached 5.5 percent in 2018.

The rapid development of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the global market, and its innovative applications have significantly influenced all sectors of the economy. The aftereffects of such intensive advancements of ICT can be summarized with these two broad outcomes – economic dimension and social dimension. The economic dimension of ICT is described with the computerization of most human tasks, that enabled businesses to significantly upgrade the traditional process of service delivery. In fact, the widespread application of ICT in the global market resulted in the following main aftereffects – creation of high-paying jobs, growth of productivity and GDP, rise of high growth companies, creation of new sectors and ways of doing business, increase of competitive advantage; and promotion of Innovation in all sectors of the economy (Atkinson & Stewart, 2013).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Concurrently, the social dimension of ICT can be recapped with the emergence of the new modes of human behavior and communication. These widespread developments in the ICT field have significantly upgraded the way people interact and communicate with each other. For instance, the emergence of social networking platforms (such as Facebook, Google+, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube and others), as well as the expanded power of content delivered through them,

have significantly upgraded the power of consumers in the global market, no matter of the business size, maturity or expertise in the field. Pulizi (2016) defines this tendency with four key factors - *decrease in technological barriers; the rise of amateur; the rise of online communities; and the rapid expansion of content and its influence.*

Indeed, digitalization of the economy incorporates the various forms of products and services emerged with the growth of the power and reach of ICT. Recent alterations in the global economy with the sharp improvement of ICT, demands the reassessment of the industry classification for the Internet platforms and Internet enabled services. More specifically, a vivid illustration of what is covered under the information and communication services; as well as clear adaptations on the classification of digital products and services should be reconsidered.

This concern ignited with the low productivity growth of advanced economies during the rapid technological progress in the world, that is argued to be a consequence of the digital economy mismeasurement in GDP. Subsequently, IMF describes these inaccuracies as a result of the lack of generally agreed definition of the digital economy (sector, products and transactions), that often results in a very narrow description of the concept «digital economy», considering it only as online platforms and its associated activities. In fact, all activities that involve digitized data are part of the digital economy (Reinsdorf, Quiros, & STA Group, 2018).

To clarify, OECD suggests the approach of distinguishing digital transactions (digitally ordered, digitally delivered and platform-enabled) to identify the products and services of the digital sector (Reinsdorf, Quiros, & STA Group, 2018) (see Annex 1). Despite the fact that the significance of digital trade is growing, the proposed general framework by OECD lacks to describe the data sources and methods for innovative business models, such as Facebook, Uber, Airbnb and others.

These and other further concerns highlight the crucial need to develop updated, improved and internationally agreed descriptions, classifications and measurement methods of the elements of digital economy. The research will not further discuss the challenges and consequences of the lack of reliable conceptual and measurement framework of the components of modern digital economy. Instead, the existing classifications and measurement regimes will be reviewed with the aim to provide a conceptual guideline for the current work. The proposed definition and classification of the concept «Information and communication services» do not claim to replace any of the current international classification frameworks, but rather is developed with the aim to identify the national services covered under this description, and serve as a fundamental guideline for the research.

Measurement classification regimes of services sector: Even though, the classifications, which were created by the WTO constructed the landmark for the discussions of any classifications, it could not be overrated that owing to their original date, the fast and continuing technological enhancements since the Uruguay Round (1986-1994) and the shortage of significant amendments in the WTO regime ever since, more current classifications of other organizations are introduced and are made use of in international trade negotiations. The following paragraphs aim to review these classification regimes (see Table 1).

Table 1
Comparative analysis of services sector measurement classification regimes.

CLASSIFICATION REGIMES	GENERAL DESCRIPTION AND LATEST UPDATES	LIMITATIONS
W/120	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Complete listing of services sectors and sub-sectors covered under GATS. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Services offered through Internet were not legitimate during the negotiations of the Uruguay Round (1986-1994), and there is a shortage of significant amendments in the WTO regime ever since.
The Central Product Classification (CPC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Based on physical features of products or on the origin of the provided services; ✓ Significant improvements made to keep up with technological progress (particularly telecommunications and internet services list has been extended). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Although telecommunications and internet services list have been improved, the services enabled through internet platforms (such as Airbnb), and media sectors have not been considered.
International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) of the United Nations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Defines Information and Communications Technology (ICT) sector, as well as Content and Media Sectors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The services provided through the internet platforms have not been included (such as Airbnb).
The Joint OECD – Eurostat Trade in Services Classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Close link to the fifth edition BPM; ✓ Covers all service transactions made between residents and non-residents. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The innovative services provided in the digital economy have not been reviewed.
Manual on Statistics of International Trade in Services (MSITS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Widely implemented to measure international negotiations on trade in services; ✓ Observing enhancements in the market of international services; ✓ A thorough classification of services distributed via traditional trade 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Distinguishes only among telecommunications, computer and information services; ✓ Digital transactions have been considered.

	between residents and non-residents; ✓ The classification of Extended Balance of Payments (EBOPS) and existing frameworks for statistics has been revised.	
Extended Balance of Payments offerings (EBOPS)	✓ Close to IMF's BPM5 classification of trade in services; ✓ Describes electronic services through dividing into two wide sectors (Communication services; Computer and Information services).	✓ Does not include complete list of services provided through the Internet platforms, digital products/services.
Nations International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC)	✓ Standardized internationally to classify productive economic activities; ✓ Allows entities to be classified according to the activity they perform.	✓ Online platforms (Google, Facebook) and their products are incomplete, as well as platform-enabled services are not included (Airbnb).

W/120: The services sectoral category list (W/120) is a complete listing of services sectors and sub-sectors covered under GATS. It was assembled by the WTO in July 1991 and its aim was to moderate the Uruguay Round negotiations, safeguarding cross country similarity and consistency of the dedications guarantee. The 160 sub-sectors are illustrated a grand total of the more thorough categories incorporated in the United Nations Provisional Central Product Classification (CPC). Based on the CPC the W/120 contains a diminished variant of it, giving a less understandable demonstration of sectors and sub-sectors (Weber & Mira, 2013).

The Central Product Classification (CPC Version 1.1, 2002): CPC is, in fact, a categorization which is based on the physical features of products or on the origin of the provided services. Every sort of product or service differentiated in the CPC is described as an avenue that is usually created by solely one activity as clarified in International Standard Industry Classification of all Economic Activities (ISIC). The CPC deals with goods that are an outcome of the activities in the field of Economy, which contains transportable goods, non-transportable products and services.

Supplying a framework for the international comparison of statistics relating to goods is, in fact, the primary objective of the CPC. Besides, it serves as a guide for developing or revising existing classification schemes of products in order to make them compatible with international standards.

The renewal to CPC 1.1 has concentrated largely on improving the structure and detailed scrutiny of certain sections of CPC 1.0. The updates to the set of CPC for 2002 also deal with telecommunications. A restructuring and ongoing scrutiny of groups 841 and 842 under division 84 were introduced along with the fast technological changes and appearing needs in products and

services in telecommunications. CPC 1.1 provides a more detailed structure by type of telecommunications service. More specifically, these updates include carrier services, fixed telephone services, mobile telecommunications services and program distribution services. A more elaborate breakdown and detailed study of Internet related services under group 842 have also been enhanced.

CPC 2.0 (CPC Version 2) being the most recent revision (completed on 31 December 2008) of the international unity of economic and social classifications contains a detailed classification of all products and services and is the standard for all goods that are an outcome of an economic activity.

The Joint OECD - Eurostat Trade in Services Classification (OECD): OECD has a close link to the fifth edition BPM (BPM5). It can be featured as a disaggregation of the BPM 5 classification for balance of payments transactions related to trade in services. The Joint OECD-Eurostat Trade in Services Classification compiles all service transactions made between residents and non-residents. The estimate of every member country's exports and imports of services by service type is indicated by the database on «International Trade in Services» (Weber & Mira, 2013).

Manual of Statistics of International Trade in Services (MSITS): The Guide that was made on Statistics of International Trade in Services 2010 (MSITS 2010) deals with the needs of a range of goods and users of such statistics. It is mainly a manual for compilers of statistics, while it is at the same time a handy tool for governments and international organizations too that implement statistical data dealing with international negotiations on trade in services. Moreover, it can sustain enterprises and others while observing enhancements in the market of international services.

RESULTS

The updated guide supplies a more thorough classification of services distributed via traditional trade between residents and non-residents than is contained in BPM6. There have been made revisions in the classification of Extended Balance of Payments Services (EBOPS 2010) and existing frameworks for statistics (Weber & Mira, 2013).

The MSITS 2010 Classification follows the BPM6 approach, hence differentiating among telecommunications, computer and information services, further disaggregated as follows (OECD):

1) «Telecommunications services» deals with the release of broadcasts or transmission of sound, illustrations, information, or other data by phone, telex, telegram, radio and television cable transmission, radio and television satellite, electronic mail, facsimile, and others which also covers the network of business services, teleconferencing, and support services. The items which are not incorporated are the value of the data transported, the mobile telecommunications services, the Internet backbone services and online access services.

2) The constituent elements of «Computer services» are hardware- and software-related services and information processing services. The nest peculiarity is executed between computer software and other computer offerings (consultancy, installation, maintenance and repair, data recovery services).

3) News agency offerings and other data services (such as database services, database conception, data storage, and dissemination of data) are in fact the constituent parts of the 'the information services'.

Extended Balance of Payments (EBOPS): While it is more detailed, the classification of the EBOPS is generally similar to IMF's BPM5 classification of trade in services. EBOPS was

made for the MSITS 2002, deriving from the experience obtained with the usage of the Joint OECD-Eurostat Trade in Services Classification at the end of the 1990s. EBOPS is a disaggregation of the joint OECD - Eurostat Trade in Services Classification, and describes electronic services through dividing it into two wide sectors: 1) Communication services; 2) Computer and information services as presented in Picture 1.1.1.

Nations International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC): ISIC is known to be the United Nations International Standard Industrial Classification of every economic activity. This classification is standardized internationally to classify productive economic activities in order to allow entities to be able to be classified with regard to the activity they perform (Weber & Mira, 2013).

DISCUSSION

Since there is no single internationally recognized description of the word «services» owing to the fact that the opposing parties could not come to consensus, the meaning of «services» is subject to interpretations (Weber & Mira, 2013). According to the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics «services» are the result of productive activities that change the state of consumers (legal entities and individuals) or facilitates the exchange of goods, services or financial assets (Methodical provisions, 2016). Statistical records of services by type of economic activity are maintained in accordance with the Program of development of the services sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of 02.26.2016 No. 55 "On the program of development of the services sector for 2016-2020", and distinguishes 13 main sectors of services by economic activity (see Picture 1).

Picture 1. Electronic Services: based on the EBOPS classification regime.

However, the research found that the currently available classification regimes (see Picture 1.1.2) do not consider (or partly consider) three crucial trends in the services sector, empowered with the recent digital advancements in the global economy: 1) Online platforms (Google, Facebook, Davra.uz) and their products; 2) Platform-enabled services (such as Airbnb, Uber, MyTaxi and others); 3) Databases are considered as a product, but not data itself.

Certainly, IT sector has expanded out of a merge of telecommunications, computer technology and software and the mixture with services from more content-focused sectors such as broadcasting and publicizing were to come in the future, which is resulting in a mix hybrid IT

services cloud and consequently hard to put into categories into any specific sector.

Picture 2. The main services sectors of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Based on the reviews of relevant studies, the following definition of the concept of Information and Communication services is developed by the author as a baseline to continue the current research: «*Information and communication services (ICS) are those services that are provided through the digital transactions (digitally ordered/platform enabled/digitally delivered), telecommunications and social networks*». The proposed definition covers three major services sectors:

1) *Services provided through the digital transactions*: Digital commodities could be computer software, videos, images, sound recordings or other commodities that are digitally encoded and transmitted through the electronic devices, despite whether they are contractually treated as commodities or services. Frequently, the trade with digital commodities has the feature of a service, because the users have an interest in the data (software, video) that can be a byproduct of digital product. Therefore, there is mostly a close linkage to a service, since the digital products are seen as services notwithstanding the way the product/service is offered or consumed.

Furthermore, the continuous and irrepressible development of the Internet and Internet-related services along with the ubiquitous ongoing progress of other data and ICT devices is improving electronic cross-border communication of services and digital commodities (such as the recordings of sound, audiovisual works, video games, computer programs and literary works). Therefore, and importantly, services provided through digital transactions should be included to this sector.

2) *Telecommunication services*: Telecommunication services is a broad group of services, that does not limit with mobile and Internet services. The contemporary telecommunication services cover voice communication, telex/telegraph/facsimile services, analogue/digital cellular/cellphone services, mobile data services, as well as electronic and voice mails, electronic data interchange, online database retrieval and others. WTO distinguishes basic and value-added

telecommunication services, that is presented in the complete W/120 (see Picture 1.1.3) (Weber & Mira, 2013).

2) *Social Networks*: A social network is usually described as a «construct» encompassing relationships between individuals, groups, organizations, or even entire societies. The structure of a social network is determined by interactions between persons or entities. The characteristics of a social network are expressed by such interactions which often model and explain social phenomena. Technically, online storage and retrieval of data is at the forefront.

The notion of social networks (for instance *Facebook* or *Twitter*) normally is made up of sharing principles and beliefs across communities, and in the meantime shaping social bonds between those who are taking part in the network and, therefore, creating social groups. Social networks established in the Internet were not in existence during the Uruguay Round negotiations; as a result, the electronic services belonging to social networks are not recognized and listed in any classification modes while being utilized at the beginning of nineties.

Services provided by a social network normally are not charged to those taking part. This, in fact, makes social networks appealing. However, payments are not inappropriate; the services for advertising provide the financial needs of a social network and provide it with the possibility not to enquire money from the users («consumers»). Businesses which are interested to attain a large public usually purchase virtual space. Hence, it can be said that advertising is the major profit source for a social network.

Picture 3. Basic and value-added sectors of telecommunication services under W/120 list

The categorization of services in the digital economy is known to be principle for running businesses not only in the ICT-related fields; but at the same time, it seems to be a particularly difficult regulatory problem, which effects on a range and often hard problems. The principle idea of classification is to group and organize information while making it meaningful and systematic according to a standard model that is handy for identifying the comparability of services.

Nevertheless, there does not exist any agreed framework or conceptual prototype that contains all aspects and the ever-progressing behavior of the information society. The illustrations of a variety of classification regimes and standards have demonstrated that a number of international organizations having various aims are collaborating on the enhancement and development of internationally applicable standards on the services sector.

CONCLUSION

1. Marketing activities of companies operating in the sphere of information and communication services require the implementation of innovative and modern technologies as part of their activities developed towards the promotion of digital economy in Uzbekistan. The scientific-theoretical classification and systematization of the main types and tools of SMM generated according to the analysis of the available theoretical concepts and methodological developments in the field of innovative marketing, will serve in the effective organizations of these actions.

2. The prospective ways (SMM, virtual reality, internet of things, artificial intelligence) of advancing information and communication services market through using advanced marketing technologies, that are developed based on the analysis and systematization of innovative marketing strategies, enabled with the rapid improvement of web technologies have been identified.

3. The marketing capabilities of national companies in the field of information and communication services have been expanded through the implementation of innovative marketing strategies - content marketing, SMM, crowdsourcing and mobile marketing.

4. The potential ways of improving the efficiency of content marketing strategies under the SMM activities of the companies operating within the information and communication services market through the establishment of corporate blogs and e-newsletter subscriptions is justified. Furthermore, considering that the popularity of e-mail usage among the population of Uzbekistan is significantly lower than the mobile messengers, the promotion of the brand e-newsletter subscriptions through messenger channels, groups and boards (specifically, telegram messenger) ensures the establishment of effective communication methods between consumers and the company, as well as increase the levels of consumer satisfaction with the company's services.

5. The competitiveness of the companies operating in the market of information and communication services of Uzbekistan are increased through the implementation of innovative mobile marketing techniques (including NFC, mobile wallet, Bluetooth marketing, mobile optimized web sites, mobile application, mobile commerce, and QR codes) with the purpose to improve the services provided by e-commerce platforms and promote non-cash payments that will increase the access to these platforms.

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